

Spatially Dependent Photometric Activity of M dwarfs in the Solar Cylinder

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Abstract

We present a follow-up study of the relationship between Galactic spatial distribution (R, Z) and photometric activity for 3.6 million M dwarf stars within ± 1 kpc from the Sun. For this work, we collect 906 unique flare events (proxy for magnetic activity) from SkyMapper Data Release 3. By adopting the vertical distance $|Z|$ from the Galactic disc as proxy for age, we confirm a strong trend of flaring fraction decreasing with growing stellar age. Moreover, we find a hint of a kink in the slope of the overall flare fraction near 100 pc from the plane, where a steep decline begins. The slope change is visible for mid-type M dwarfs (M3–M5), suggesting it is not an artefact of mixing spectral type. As probed by other activity indicator, SDSS H α observations, this trend could be a additional evidence that the activity fraction of M dwarfs depends on Galactic height as well as activity lifetime. While there is a weak sign of flattening of the overall activity fraction above $|Z| = 500$ pc, our data do not constrain this further. Within ~ 500 pc distance from the Sun, we find no sign of radial disk gradients in flare activity.

1 Spatially Dependent Photometric Activity

The strength of M dwarf activity decreases as the stars get older, which is revealed by several activity tracers such as X-ray, H α , white-light flare emissions, and even size of starspot and its surface coverage. There is a clear evidence that the H α activity fraction of M dwarfs decreases with increasing height $|Z|$ above the Galactic plane (West *et al.*, 2006, 2008, 2011) and depends on location (R, Z) in the Galaxy (Pineda *et al.*, 2013). With M dwarfs flares in near-simultaneous, multi-filter observations, Kowalski *et al.* (2009) found similar evidence of age-dependent flaring activity. Recently, Chang *et al.* (2020) also confirmed the trend of decreasing flaring fraction with $|Z|$ more clearly than before. All these behaviours are a natural consequence of well-known age-rotation-activity relation (Skumanich, 1972), which is further supported by kinematic evidence of increasing velocity dispersion of stars V_z/σ_{V_z} and their scale heights $|Z|$ with age (e.g., Sharma *et al.* 2021).

To assess the link between the observed activity trend and age distribution, we use a statistical approach to get reliable mean ensemble properties (age and activity fraction) for an M dwarf sample rather than individual stars. We recommend readers refer to Chang *et al.* (2022) for this work in detailed description and further results.

2 Single M dwarfs in the Solar Cylinder

We use the third data release of the SkyMapper Southern Survey (SMSS DR3) to extract a new sample of single M dwarfs. DR3 includes observations from March 2014 to October 2019, more than doubling the deep coverage over the previous data release (DR2: Onken *et al.* 2019), which is currently accessible to world-wide users. Following the

procedure described in Chang *et al.* (2020), we initially select an extended sample of 13.6 million M dwarf candidates. To identify likely main sequence stars, we use high-precision astrometric and photometric measurements from Gaia’s early data release 3 (EDR3; Gaia Collaboration *et al.*, 2016, 2021). We finally apply several quality cuts recommended by the Gaia Collaboration to obtain a clean sample (e.g., Riello *et al.* 2021; Lindegren *et al.* 2021). As a result, we obtain a flux-limited sample of about 3.6 million objects with red colours, $G_R - G_B > 0.9$, which is about two times larger than our previous work. This sample includes M dwarfs with a wide range of ages and/or metallicity in the Galactic disc out to $|Z| \sim 1$ kpc away from the Galactic mid-plane. In this analysed volume, we expect populations with an average age of 4–5 Gyr (e.g., Casali *et al.* 2019; Bland-Hawthorn *et al.* 2019).

3 Proxy for Magnetic Activity: White-Light Flares

Several multi-band, time-series surveys have reported rapidly changing spectral energy distributions (SEDs) as a signature of M dwarf flares (e.g., Kowalski *et al.* 2009; Davenport *et al.* 2012; Osten *et al.* 2012; Chang *et al.* 2020). Although the measurements of these flare SEDs are limited by the temporal resolution, it still allows to investigate how often they occur.

DR3 provides the time-series photometry table where we construct light curves of M dwarfs in six *uvgriz* photometric bands. Thanks to SMSS survey strategy, each observation blocks contains near-simultaneous, multi-filter exposures within a 4 minute-visit or 20 minute-visit. The Shallow Survey uses a filter sequence of the form [*u-v-g-r-i-z*] with exposure times of 40, 20, 5, 5, 10 and 20 seconds, respectively.

Figure 1: Flaring (solid lines) and quiescent (dashed lines) SEDs of M1–M8 dwarfs with large continuum enhancement. Solid circles indicate the location of the central filter wavelength of u , v , g , r , i , and z bands.

In contrast, the Main Survey has a colour sequence of the form $[u-v-g-r-u-v-i-z-u-v]$ with a uniform exposure time of 100 seconds. The Main Survey also collects additional exposure pairs in $g-r$ and $i-z$ on different nights.

With the benefit of near-simultaneous, broadband data in SMSS DR3, we find 1,379 candidate epochs among ~ 42 million observed epochs in any filter combinations, which contains 933 unique flare candidates in total. The number of M dwarf flares is increased by factor of 3.5 compared to our previous work. Thanks to the contrast effect, flaring M dwarfs have a good visibility in the uv g bands or even in the redder filters (see Figure 1).

4 Dynamical Proxy for Age: $|Z|$

We adopt vertical distance $|Z|$ from the Galactic disc as a dynamical proxy for age. As shown in Figure 2, the photometric activity fractions decrease as a function of Galactic height, confirming again a strong trend of flaring fraction decreasing with growing stellar age (e.g., West *et al.* 2008; Kowalski *et al.* 2009; Ilin *et al.* 2019, 2021; Chang *et al.* 2020). Interestingly, we find a hint of a *kink* in the slope of the flare fraction near 100 pc from the Galactic plane where a steep decline sets in. This unexplained slope change is also visible for mid-type M dwarfs, M3–M5, suggesting it is not an artefact of mixing spectral type or the binning procedure. A mech-

Figure 2: Fraction of flaring epochs as a function of $|Z|$ from the Galactic plane with an equal bin size of 10 pc (gray points) and the black points are those with the equal bin size of 25 pc only up to 250 pc. To increase a resolution in $|Z|$ on the distant tail over 250 pc, we adjust the width of the $|Z|$ bins that have a constant number of flare events (red points).

anism for producing kinks may be a bottleneck in the dynamical heating; stars move quickly away from the Galactic plane at first but then slow down as they spend a decreasing fraction of their time in the high-density disk plane. Thus, it would be interesting to check the vertical profile for active stars of other spectral types as well.

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References

- Bland-Hawthorn, J., Sharma, S., Tepper-Garcia, T., Binney, J., Freeman, K. C., *et al.* 2019, MNRAS, 486, 1167.
- Casali, G., Magrini, L., Tognelli, E., Jackson, R., Jeffries, R. D., *et al.* 2019, A&A, 629, A62.
- Chang, S.-W., Wolf, C., & Onken, C. A. 2020, MNRAS, 491, 39.
- Chang, S.-W., Wolf, C., & Onken, C. A. 2022, MNRAS, 517, 2842.
- Davenport, J. R. A., Becker, A. C., Kowalski, A. F., Hawley, S. L., Schmidt, S. J., *et al.* 2012, ApJ, 748, 58.
- Gaia Collaboration, Brown, A. G. A., Vallenari, A., Prusti, T., de Bruijne, J. H. J., *et al.* 2021, A&A, 649, A1.
- Gaia Collaboration, Prusti, T., de Bruijne, J. H. J., Brown, A. G. A., Vallenari, A., *et al.* 2016, A&A, 595, A1.

- Ilin, E., Schmidt, S. J., Davenport, J. R. A., & Strassmeier, K. G. 2019, *A&A*, 622, A133.
- Ilin, E., Schmidt, S. J., Poppenhäger, K., Davenport, J. R. A., Kristiansen, M. H., *et al.* 2021, *A&A*, 645, A42.
- Kowalski, A. F., Hawley, S. L., Hilton, E. J., Becker, A. C., West, A. A., *et al.* 2009, *AJ*, 138, 633.
- Lindgren, L., Bastian, U., Biermann, M., Bombrun, A., de Torres, A., *et al.* 2021, *A&A*, 649, A4.
- Onken, C. A., Wolf, C., Bessell, M. S., Chang, S.-W., Da Costa, G. S., *et al.* 2019, , 36, e033.
- Osten, R. A., Kowalski, A., Sahu, K., & Hawley, S. L. 2012, *ApJ*, 754, 4.
- Pineda, J. S., West, A. A., Bochanski, J. J., & Burgasser, A. J. 2013, *AJ*, 146, 50.
- Riello, M., De Angeli, F., Evans, D. W., Montegriffo, P., Carrasco, J. M., *et al.* 2021, *A&A*, 649, A3.
- Sharma, S., Hayden, M. R., Bland-Hawthorn, J., Stello, D., Buder, S., *et al.* 2021, *MNRAS*, 506, 1761.
- Skumanich, A. 1972, *ApJ*, 171, 565.
- West, A. A., Bochanski, J. J., Hawley, S. L., Cruz, K. L., Covey, K. R., *et al.* 2006, *AJ*, 132, 2507.
- West, A. A., Hawley, S. L., Bochanski, J. J., Covey, K. R., Reid, I. N., *et al.* 2008, *AJ*, 135, 785.
- West, A. A., Morgan, D. P., Bochanski, J. J., Andersen, J. M., Bell, K. J., *et al.* 2011, *AJ*, 141, 97.